

Identity Formation in Indian Adolescents: A Qualitative Inquiry

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The age of social media impacts adolescents' decision-making and self-perception, and with the difference in the cultural context in India, where there is dependence on parents during adolescence, parental expectations, and strict parenting, there lies an urgent need to explore the identity formation of Indian adolescents. The aim of this study was threefold: (1) to understand how Indian adolescents perceive and understand their personal identity, (2) to understand the impact of social media on their identity development, and (3) to understand how parents and peers impact their identity development. The present study is based upon a qualitative research design grounded in the phenomenological approach. The researchers used a semi-structured interview schedule and interviewed 12 adolescents (five males & seven females; age range: 15-18 years). After receiving consent from each participant, the interview was audio recorded and manually transcribed by researchers. Data was analysed using thematic analysis based on the conceptualisation given by Braun and Clarke. The results were analysed from a social constructivist approach. Five major themes were developed and suggested that the identity development in Indian adolescents is a work in progress wherein they are still exploring themselves. It suggested the significant role of social media and parents while highlighting the mixed role of culture and self-exploration. It also revealed friendship as a support system for adolescents.

Keywords: Identity, adolescents, Indian adolescents, qualitative research, social media

Adolescence is the period marked by identity formation with the ongoing start of puberty. During this stage of life, adolescents seek answers related to their identity. They often ask themselves questions like; "who am I?" and "what would I like to be" in different life domains (e.g., relationships, vocation, beliefs, values & religion) (Schwartz et al., 2013). In recent years, several identity theories have been developed, for example, narrative identity theory (McAdams, 2011). However, the theory of Erik Erikson remains a dominant theoretical framework of identity formation during adolescence, and is also referred to as the godfather of all identity theories (Schwartz et al., 2013). It proposes the successful theory of identity development, "identity vs. role confusion," where adolescents struggle with forming a coherent sense of self. His initial emphasis lay on the advantages of having achieved the sense of "sameness and continuity" (navigating the sense of self through social interactions & experiences). Nevertheless, adolescents are often concerned with questions such as "Who am I?", "How am I perceived by others?", and "Who do I wish to become?". As described by Erikson (1968) identity development is a lifelong process, with adolescence being a critical and significant period for resolving life-defining questions of who you are, what is important in your life, and what you are pursuing in life. During this stage, if

adolescents fail to find answers to these important questions, they often suffer from identity crisis. Erikson described this state as identity confusion, wherein they contemplate their own values, beliefs, goals and personifications they identify with throughout their lives (Erikson, 1968).

Erikson's bipolar framework was operationalised by Marcia (1966). She described the process of identity formation in a four-status approach and highlighted a detailed analysis of the process. The four identity statuses are identity achievement, moratorium, foreclosure and diffusion. These domains are built upon two important dimensions of exploration and commitment. Identity achievement signifies that the adolescent has actively completed the exploration and made a commitment to a specific identity of his own; moratorium signifies that the adolescent is actively exploring his identity, but has not made any commitment because of non-clarity or confusion; foreclosure means that the adolescent has made a commitment without exploring; and diffusion indicates that the adolescent is neither exploring different alternatives nor has made any commitment (Marcia, 1966). Adolescents who have achieved their identity have gone through a period of both exploration and have made identity-defining commitments (Marcia, 1980). Identity-diffused individuals seem to drift aimlessly and are carefree. Identity diffusion tends to be associated with delinquency, low self-esteem, and drug or alcohol problems (Luyckx, Goossens, Soenens, Beyers, & Vansteenkiste, 2005; Adams, Munro, Munro, Doherty-Poirer, & Edwards, 2005). Foreclosed identity tends to make commitments without having in-depth exploration, usually by observing their parental figures or because of imposed identity by their parents (Marcia, 1966). The period of exploration that precedes commitment is referred to as a period of "moratorium," when one is able to explore and experiment with different potential identities and thus achieve their identity (Marcia, 1966). In India, it can usually be observed that adolescents have a foreclosed identity being imposed

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by the values and belief systems of their parents or family culture (Rajagopalreddy & Varghese, 2022).

At present, a relevant context for exploring and building identity in adolescents is social media and online activities (Raiziene et al., 2022). Adolescents are the most active users of social media, making online connections, bonding with peers, updating their lifestyles, and following trends. They tend to express themselves through social media (influencers, YouTubers, vloggers, Instagrammers, & creators), which has become an integral part of their lifestyle. Recent literature has significantly highlighted that social media has become a medium where adolescents socialize leading to their identity construction (Lajnef, 2023; Meier & Johnson, 2022; Valkenburg, 2022; Shankleman et al., 2021). Digital spaces like Instagram, Facebook and Twitter provide adolescents an opportunity to interact, display, and receive feedback about themselves. This immediately contributes to exploration of their identity and the formation of their self-concept (Cingel et al., 2022; Shankleman et al., 2021).

However, little emphasis has been placed on digital context and its influence on identity development. In the last decade, huge number of published articles on social media and adolescents has been considerably increased (Davis et al., 2020), but it majorly focuses on how social media influences their well-being and its negative consequences (e.g., problematic social media use, depression symptoms, risky behaviours) rather than on identity (Shankleman et al., 2021). In a very recent review study, four central themes were analysed in accordance with recent literature (Davis et al., 2020; Hollenbaugh, 2021; Meier & Johnson, 2022; Shankleman et al., 2021) self-presentation, social media audience, social comparison, and the role of models in an online context. This is suggestive of how the recent digital scenario has influenced the identity formation of adolescents. For example, recent studies suggest that connections formed on social media hinder the relationships that adolescents create with their peers or friends (Hoffner & Bond, 2022; Shankleman et al., 2021). Moreover, the feedbacks they receive about themselves does not always come from people close to them, but rather from an online audience without limit (Popovac & Hadlington, 2020; Ranzini & Hoek, 2017). Online audiences produce an empowering feeling of self-presentation (Shankleman et al., 2021) negative consequences (e.g., surveillance), and risky behaviours (Popovac & Hadlington, 2020). Therefore, the role of social media audiences in the adolescent identity process requires further evidence.

Moreover, existing research highlights how parenting plays a vital role in shaping adolescents' character (Banstola et al., 2020; Smith-Adcock et al., 2019) while also influencing their psychosocial growth and behavioural patterns (Sugiarti et al., 2021; Tulip et al., 2020). The traits adolescents develop are largely molded by their parents at home and tend to become more pronounced as they mature (Huang et al., 2021; Lin & Chiao, 2020). Scholars from earlier decades have emphasized that the way parents raise their children and the social dynamics within the family can either support or obstruct a young person's ability to navigate the challenges of adolescence (Ainsworth, 1982; Grotevant & Cooper, 1985; Zimmermann & Becker-Stoll, 2002). Puberty often marks a turning point where teenagers begin to pull away from their families, frequently clashing with their parents. These conflicts typically revolve around the adolescent's desire for autonomy (Collins & Laursen, 2004). When parents demonstrate nurturing and constructive parenting styles, their children tend to emulate those

behaviours (Green et al., 2018; Thoma et al., 2021). This indicates that when parents offer a loving atmosphere balanced with reasonable control, greater freedom, minimal punishment, open communication, and emotional support, they create space for adolescents to explore different aspects of themselves and eventually commit to a clear sense of identity. On the other hand, parenting approaches that rely heavily on strict rules and rigid discipline can make it harder for adolescents to adjust during this phase. In families where harsh control is paired with emotional coldness and punitive measures, adolescents may openly defy their parents' expectations as a way to assert their independence in a bold and visible manner (Hill & Holmbeck, 1986).

Rationale of the Study

There are very few studies done on identity formation of Indian adolescents and the impact of social media on identity formation. India is a country with various cultures, views, and morals and a distinct parenting style. It is necessary to understand how family, parenting, peers, and society affect the Indian adolescent identity formation. Indian parenting not only brings out the best in the child and acts as a source of encouragement, but sometimes it also creates a burden on the child by having unrealistic expectations. Therefore, there is an urgent need to address the role of an adolescent's social circle in shaping their identity. Furthermore, living in a world where social media helps shape an adolescent's personality, it is necessary to understand that it plays a crucial role in the formation of identity as well. From looking up to the role models and setting goals to keep up with ever-evolving trends leading to a decrease in self-esteem, social media does it all. Therefore, it is essential to understand and adapt to the role that social media plays in adolescent identity formation.

Research Questions

- How do Indian adolescents perceive and understand their personal identity?
- How is social media impacting their identity development?
- How are parents and peers impacting their identity development?

Method

Participants

Since the study is a qualitative approach, probability sampling was not possible. Therefore, non-probability sampling was undertaken. This method limits the fair selection of participants into the sample, as each member of the population does not have an equal chance of getting selected in the study. Under this non-probability approach, convenience sampling was used to select the participants. As suggested by Bernard (2002) and Spradley (1979) there is an importance of willingness and availability to participate and the ability to communicate experiences and opinions in an expressive, articulate, and reflective manner in the selected sample. Therefore, a total of 12 available and willing adolescents (five males & seven females; age range: 15-18 years) participated in the study, which included students studying in schools, all located in Delhi, India. All the participants belonged to different schools in Delhi. The participants were high school students belonging to the 11th and 12th standards. All the interviews were conducted in the park area of the societies located at different places in Delhi, India.

Research Design

The present study is qualitative research based on the phenomenological research design. A phenomenological methodology was adapted to understand the lived experiences of participants regarding their formation of identity. The research is grounded in the principles of social constructivism, which emphasizes how individuals construct and interpret their social realities. Given the aim of the study—understanding identity development in adolescents and their perceived influence of parents and social media—a combination of phenomenology with constructivist epistemology was best suited to apprehend the depth of individual experiences, since it not only captures what participants experience but also how they interpret and make sense of these experiences through shared meanings and discourses. This approach assisted in the exploration of how adolescents interpret their own identity and the role of external factors that have shaped their identity. Phenomenology provided the methodological foundation, and social constructivism informs the interpretative lens through which data is analysed.

Measures

Interview Schedule: A semi-structured interview was created by the research team using information from the literature as well as their experience. The participants were briefed about the study, and consent was received. The average duration for the interview was 20 to 30 minutes. To guide the interview process, here are examples of a few questions asked during the interview:

- If I ask, “who are you?” How would you describe yourself?
- How engaged are you with social media?
- What kind of social media content do you engage with?
- Do you think social media has a role to play in shaping you and your identity? I want you to describe your answer
- Do you think your family culture and parental expectations have any role to play in shaping your identity?
- Is your identity self-explored or an influence of others?

Transcription and Analysis: All the interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed manually by the researcher to eliminate any errors and develop a deeper understanding of the responses provided by the participants. Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis was used for analysis. The analysis was based upon the assumption that people construct their own realities through their interaction with society. Therefore, a social constructionist perspective was used as a base for analysis.

Six steps were followed that included 1) familiarisation with the data set, 2) developing primary codes, 3) developing primary themes, 4) reviewing the themes, 5) adequate defining and naming the codes, and 6) formulating and writing the whole report.

Researcher's Reflexivity: The research was carried out by a team of two researchers with distinct positionalities. The first researcher is a high school student who collected the data and conducted the interviews. The relatively close age of the researcher with the participants, as well as her non-authoritative status, helped the participants to be more open and feel comfortable. However, being new to qualitative research, she was still learning to navigate the flow of conversations and ask deeper, more insightful questions during the interviews. The second researcher is a psychologist with experience in qualitative methods who oversaw the research design,

provided guidance during the data collection, and led the process of analysis while noting the insights from the first researcher. In order to ensure reflexivity, both researchers engaged in debriefing sessions at regular intervals for the purpose of examining their assumptions, discussing the emerging insights, and challenging interpretations. This collaboration led to a balanced perspective from an insider (adolescent perspective) and outsider (professional psychological lens), ultimately enriching the depth and validity of the findings.

Results and Discussion

This section represents and discusses the themes generated from the Reflexive Thematic Analysis. There are five themes underlining the identity formation in Indian adolescents; Forming a sense of self, double role of social media, cultural context to guiding structure and moral compass, self-exploration vs external influence and the role of peers. A pictorial description is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1

A Pictorial Representation of the Themes Generated from the Analysis

Theme 1: Forming a Sense of Self: "Who am I?" A Work in Progress

This theme discusses the adolescents' understanding of their identity, and while it highlights how they define themselves, it was noted that not everyone knows who they are. Many adolescents described themselves using emotional (e.g., kind, calm), relational (e.g., sister, friend), or aspirational terms (e.g., ambitious, confident). Identity was deeply contextualized in relationships (family, siblings, friends), aligning with Marcia's Identity Status Theory, where many showed signs of *identity exploration* and *moratorium* (i.e., individuals are exploring their identity & have not made a commitment yet), and some appeared in *identity foreclosure* (i.e., accepting parental values without deep questioning).

"I haven't figured it all out yet, but I know the people I love are shaping me." - Interview 12

A few participants directly stated they were still figuring themselves out, reflecting the psychosocial moratorium and what Erik Erikson identified in his Theory of Psychosocial Development (Stage 5: *Identity vs. Role Confusion*). This theory states that adolescents start questioning themselves, "Who am I?" and exploring their values, beliefs, and morals, and if they are supported in this stage, they are likely to emerge with a strong sense of self. Role confusion suggests adolescents may struggle with finding their identity, leading to confusion and making them unsure about their role in this world. Adolescents displayed reflexivity—where they

were able to reflect on the self-but also ambiguity, as many acknowledged being in a transitional phase and not knowing their sense of self or their identity.

I'm still figuring that out. I'm just a person trying to understand myself and the world around me. Some days I feel confident and sure of who I am, and other days I feel unsure. Interview 8

Theme 2: Connectivity that Leads to Comparison and Creation: Double Role of Social Media

This theme highlights the influence of social media on the identity development of adolescents. All the participants, except for one, acknowledged the significant use of social media, mostly Instagram, in today's time. Responses highlighted both positive and negative effects, which mirrors current psychological debates.

The positive aspect of social media, here in this context, highlights the exploration and creation of one's identity. The theory of multiple selves (Gergen, 1991; Turkle, 1995) suggests that an individual has multiple selves, in which they engage with multiple, distinct aspects of their personality. It also acts as a medium for encouraging creative expression and self-presentation and helps in shaping identity by giving access to diverse role models and knowledge.

"Social media shows me sides of myself I didn't know existed." - Interview 12

The above response from the participant suggests how social media becomes a medium to explore themselves in a safe and anonymous space. Individuals engage in identity experimentation, where even a shy person explores their extroverted side. This might also lead to identity fragmentation, where the coherence of one's self-concept is challenged by the existence of multiple, sometimes conflicting, digital personas (Turtle, 1995).

"Social media has influenced how I present myself, but not how I truly see myself." Interview 10

Although social media acts as a digital mirror for adolescents, offering opportunities to explore identity, it also creates pressure to conform to often unrealistic standards and a feeling of not being able to match up to those expectations of society.

"Sometimes, I feel like I am not able to live up to their expectations." - Interview 7

This theme also highlights upward social comparisons (Festinger's Social Comparison Theory, 1954) amongst adolescents. This theory of upward social comparisons suggests that we tend to compare ourselves with those who we believe are better than or superior to us. This often leads to reduced self-esteem, increased anxiety, and a superficial sense of ideal identity that is reinforced by other people's lives. Their responses suggested addictive scrolling behaviour leading to reduced attention span, which is physiologically linked to dopamine loops.

It has made me question my self-worth and compare myself with others. It has made me aware and expressive but at the same time doubtful and anxious. Interview 6

"I sometimes scroll without realising, and it distracts me from studies." Interview 3

Theme 3: The Indian Family: Cultural Context to Guiding Structure and Moral Compass

This theme highlights the impact of family and parents on the development of their identities. Almost every participant acknowledged a significant influence of family, especially parents,

in shaping values, ambitions, and personality traits. This reflects the collectivist culture prevalent in Indian society, where interdependence and familial obligations are held more important than radical individualism. Parental expectations are seen as both motivational and restrictive. It was observed that families encourage responsibility, role-modelling, and empathy. For most participants, family served as a primary agent of moral development, as per Kohlberg's stages (1978) especially instilling values like honesty, humility, and discipline.

"Family's values shaped how I see right and wrong, how I treat people, and how I work toward goals. Even when I question those things, I know they helped create the foundation of who I am. Sometimes I do feel like they expect too much from me but at the end of the day, I know that it's for my betterment that they do so." - Interview 3

"Yes, I definitely see the influence of my parents on my identity, sometimes I feel like naturally I do some things that my mother used to do so I do have some of her traits that I now see in myself." Interview 5

Some participants voiced feeling pressured or unable to be their authentic selves around family, suggesting identity conflict. This aligns with the Social Identity Theory given by Turner, Brown, and Tajfel (1979) which suggests conflict between one's *personal identity* and *social identity* as defined by cultural roles as reflected by the adolescent participants.

"I appreciate my family and everything they've done for me, but sometimes I feel like I can't fully be myself around them. There are things I want to explore that don't always match their expectations, and I also feel like they have put a little too many restrictions on me as compared to the kids my age." Interview 12

"Sometimes they also make me feel like I'm not enough, sometimes I also feel the pressure of being someone who I am not." Interview 11

Theme 4: A Blended Journey: Self-exploration vs. External Influence

This theme suggests that the formation of identity amongst adolescents is a product of both self-exploration and external influence. Most adolescents described identity formation as a mix of self-exploration and social influence, indicating a dynamic process. This is in alignment with Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979) where identity is formed through interactions across various systems: microsystem (family/peers), exosystem (school/social norms), and macrosystem (cultural values, media).

When adolescents are exploring their identities, they are often tied to creative activities (music, reading, journaling), which are majorly influenced by the macrosystem in which the cultural elements affect the child's development, consisting of the cultural ideologies, attitudes, and social conditions that adolescents are immersed in. The external influences come from family, peers, social media, and school environments, which are influenced by the microsystem (an adolescent's most immediate relationships & environments, i.e., parents, siblings, classmates, teachers, & neighbours) and the exosystem (the formal & informal social setting; it does not directly interact with the adolescent, but the exosystem affects the microsystem).

Identity formation amongst adolescents appeared context-sensitive. This means that something that is encouraged in one

system may be discouraged in another (e.g., self-expression vs. conformity). Self-expression refers to communicating with one's own unique self and individuality, while conformity refers to aligning oneself with the group, their expectations, and beliefs. In this context, the adolescent chooses whether to have their own voice and form their own identities through self-exploration or conform to the social norms just to fit in.

"I've learnt things on my own, but I also carry a lot of what my parents taught me." Interview 6

Theme 5: Role of Peers: Mirrors and Catalysts

While not directly questioned, many participants referenced close friendships and school environments as sources of emotional support and validation. These findings align with Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978) where peers play a role in scaffolding social identity and helping adolescents make meaning of their place in the world.

Adolescents described that peers served as safe spaces for experimentation with identity. The social roles they had within peer groups (e.g., being the funny one or the emotional one) shaped internal narratives. Group belonging offered emotional safety a factor critical for healthy identity development. As Erik Erikson says in his identity theory, adolescents are more influenced by their peers during this stage while feeling more disconnected from their family identities; this was not reflected amongst these Indian adolescents. Friendships and peer groups were seen more as a support rather than an installation of identities.

"I love hanging out with my friends in my free time and we meet almost every day which is probably my favourite time of the day." Interview 9

"I love hanging out with my friends and they always describe me as a fun person to be around with" Interview 10

Conclusion

This study explored how Indian adolescents are developing or forming their identities. It suggested how identity formation is influenced by social media and parental relations and expectations by providing contextualised accounts of its effects on diverse adolescents of India. The data helped us understand the crucial role of parents, peer groups, and family on adolescents; the identity confusion faced by them; and the major effects that social media and family play on identity formation. In the Indian culture, parents and family play a huge role in shaping the adolescent's identity; familial obligations are given more importance than racial individualism. Parental expectations are seen as both motivational and restrictive. Some Indian parents do not provide adolescents an opportunity to explore their identity, likes, dislikes, and preferences. The adolescents often feel the pressure of being a different person around them due to their high expectations, and it often burdens them; some cannot figure out the difference between their own identity and the identity imposed on them. Others think that the expectations help them accomplish their goal, acting as a source of motivation, encouraging role-modelling and responsibility. The participants described close peer bonds and school environments as sources of emotional support and validation. They often described their personality by comparing it with the role they played in their social circles, not mentioning that their identity was shaped by the influence of their peers. Therefore, this suggests that Indian

adolescent identity is mainly influenced by parents and family values. Furthermore, social media also acts as a tool that helps identify distinct aspects of their personality by giving access to diverse role models and knowledge. It acts as a medium to explore more about themselves in an anonymous place. At the same time, it also reduces their self-esteem and increases anxiety due to the constant comparison with others, unrealistic standards, and high expectations of society. The present study also suggests addictive scrolling behaviour leading to reduced attention span and losing track of time. Many respondents described their identity using their personality traits and familial bonds; some even stated that they were still figuring themselves out, indicating that they have not fully discovered their identity yet. Most adolescents described their identity formation as a mix of self-exploration, referring to communication with one's unique self, and social influence, referring to the cultural ideologies and social conditions coming from family, peers, and social media, indicating a nuanced and dynamic process.

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